

Workshop outcomes and next steps for WP5 BOOST-EDS

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

- The ‘Co-creation of user-focussed services: priorities across the EDS - technical experts workshop’ was held online on Monday 25th March 2024 10:00am-12:00pm. Mixture of presentation and discussion sessions
- 24 attendees. All technical experts from across the Environmental Data Service (and partners). Range of expertise: software development, data management, co-creation and user experience, community building and communications.

Purpose of event

- To understand current (or near future) areas of work being undertaken on user-focussed services across the EDS (and partners)
- To identify barriers to including users in the co-creation of these services
- To create a list of potential activities that could be used as case studies for co-creating user-focussed services

Workshop summary

Before the workshop we asked attendees to provide details about their work/expertise and any barriers they have personally faced to co-creation. Attendees were also asked to identify specific user-focussed services that are being developed/improved either currently or over the next year. The details provided formed the basis of discussions in the workshop.

Discussions during the workshop were lively and positive. There were four discussion groups - each with a facilitator. Notes were taken collaboratively.

There is plenty of work already going on in the teams that could make good use cases for this work. Some teams were more experienced in co-creating services and engaging with users, whereas others understood the importance but historically it hasn't been their focus. It was clear that all attendees believed co-creation and engaging with the intended audience for services was important.

Key themes

Four key themes were identified from the workshop discussions:

1. Ineffective sharing of learnings
2. Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities
3. Lack of time/resources
4. Difficult to engage with users/stakeholders

Each has been summarised below with details of the barriers, benefits and opportunities.

1. Ineffective sharing of learning

We need to share existing information about co-creation of services more effectively and actively encourage learning from each other.

Opportunities:

For this WP:

- Ensure literature/best practice for co-creation of services is reflected in the final guidance report from this work package
- Choose case studies for testing out co-creation of services which can be used as examples to learn from

For wider EDS:

- Create a central location for sharing examples of best practice e.g. on the EDS website or via internal documents
- Create how to guides based on our existing experience e.g.
 - how to design toolkits
 - internal documentation on the data collection and engagement methods
 - As a minimum it would be useful to have a list of the different tools used by different teams.
 - User interface designs - what are the patterns that sit together of standard elements of services to serve the final purpose. [BGS example](#) of patterns for spatial data portal guidance.
 - Decision support tools - BGS draft guidance exists not yet public
 - DSH - learn from their use cases/processes. Sharing key outcomes from report and discussing implementation with EDS.
 - build on external work (ensure this is reflected in the final guidance created by this work package)

Barriers:

- Lack of visibility - not sure who to ask
- Too much information (overwhelming!)
- This will require a mindset shift within teams - historically we've been project focussed, and do not (officially) think about how the project findings can be translated into a broader perspective

Benefit:

- Reducing duplication of effort
- Improved knowledge sharing

2. Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities

Engagement between EDS peers is better than it used to be, but there is still room for improvement. There needs to be clarity about priorities and how our individual missions can contribute to the wider shared vision/goals.

Opportunities:

For this WP:

- Set up a co-creation working group with representatives from each key partner.
- Invite representatives from each DSIT-funded project to join the co-creation working group or ask DSIT to facilitate this as its own activity.
- Feed the identified barriers back to other BOOST-EDS work package leads/EDS management. Suggest the need for a project manager and regular work package lead meetings.

For wider EDS:

- List/database of staff names and their expertise/interest areas, so it becomes easier to find someone who has experience in the correct area. Needs to have predefined categories for types of roles/expertise.
- Talk to each other more - but it needs to be coordinated. Tech teams do talk to each other. Teams that talk to users could talk to each other more.
- Also training factored into developments so users can access and use the tools/services created
- Mobilising and exchanging work done within different projects (e.g. Digital Solutions work on Data Quality would be useful for EDS).
- Continue to provide ways for staff to communicate across teams (e.g. slack).
- Create an EDS vision and mission. Aim to piece together what our individual missions (including this project) are to fit in with a wider EDS vision.

Barriers:

- Lack of visibility of expertise within internal EDS teams and their partner organisations about what we are doing (not limited to this project). Not knowing who else is doing similar work (or has past experience)
- Lack of visibility of work going on in the other RDCP funded projects - don't even know what they're about. Would be good to share knowledge as the projects progress.
- Complexity of what we/EDS do.
- Legacy issues/history. Siloed data/tools.
- Lack of shared vision/mission/coordination across the project/EDS makes it difficult to explain the rationale for this work

Benefits:

- Improved knowledge sharing
- Reduce duplication of work and allow for knowledge sharing across the projects (both internal and external to the EDS).
- Reduce time spent on trying to find the right person
- Clarity of the bigger picture mission

3. Lack of time/resources

Staff are juggling lots of different priorities, and may not necessarily be involved directly in this project.

Opportunities:

For this WP:

- Choose work that is already being undertaken/planned as the co-creation case studies. Only additional requirement would be to regularly share their findings with the co-creation working group.
- Need better summaries of existing co-design work that we've done already. And how much resource it took to complete. (BGS - example, couple of weeks development time. Based on a huge body of evidence that had been collated over several years - difficult to define. Don't keep in heads of individuals.
- Encourage agile processes (e.g. asking for feedback from users on early prototype systems) to ensure we are doing things that are actually needed by users

For wider EDS:

- Using Agile processes as a common ground, something we can all implement across data centres. Already happening in many individual teams, how can we increase/expand this?
- Professional development opportunities for person/people in the team who can speak to both the users and the developers, can act as a bridge and communicate to both groups

- Unified, transparent approaches to assessing requirements prior to the establishment of infrastructure driven by specific use cases
- Define what are the core services that we're going to focus on and build upon - so that they can be prioritised.
- Keep talking about what we are doing. Especially need to think about how we can be approachable to users, not too technical but still communicative.

Barriers:

- Who is responsible for co-creation of services? Data sci, devs..??
- Lack of time to change how we do things. Lack of capacity / investment / headroom for proactive assessment / establishing of requirements
- With limited team resources, we can only do bits of work, so proper agile sprints are hard to manage.
- People without the required knowledge/skills assigned to important roles like scrum master/project manager/documentation writer
- Prioritising user engagement in data centres that have so far prioritised internal tools for the teams. Will require a mindset shift.
- Difficult to get the balance between what you are working on vs what you can show the users (e.g. API first approach would not offer much to show the users, so it becomes too abstract for users).
- Getting data in is hard and time consuming. This has historically been our key focus. Previous developments have been about improving internal processes, rather than focussing on what the users want/who they are. Will require a change in how we do things.

Benefit:

- User-focussed services will be better aligned with user requirements

4. Difficult to engage with users/stakeholders

As our data becomes more open, we increasingly struggle to know who is using our data/services. We need to know who the users are, so we can convince them to engage with us.

Opportunities:

For this WP:

- Create guidance for ways to encourage engagement with users/stakeholders e.g.
 - Be very clear about what the value of the interactions are for all involved, to encourage engagement with the work
 - Important to be transparent about the value of this type of work (to the people we're asking) e.g. why we want to co-create services, what the benefits are, what their contributions are used for etc.
- The case studies will act as examples for how to interact with users for co-creation of services

For wider EDS:

- Identify who the users are and what their issues are (as an EDS). Needs to be iterative with actionable solutions.

Barriers:

- Not clear to users what are the motivating factors for participating - not always easy to find time / motivation to participate - especially in user-focussed development work that extends current project priorities.
- Surveys are too broad. This limits the question we ask. Does not provide details on individual services much. We are worried about survey fatigue.
- Our services serve anonymous users - difficult to contact them.
- How to get users engaged e.g. you ask for feedback (banners on websites, surveys) but don't get any.
- Not knowing who the data users are to send surveys to (worse since data is becoming more open)
- Finding our users and how reach out to them. We don't know who are users are and what their issues are (as an EDS).
- API tokens and keys, and tracking is tricky. The solution was to remove registration, which also removes the knowledge of how the data is used. And you don't know who your users are.
- Getting the right people in the room is tricky. Don't want too many people in the room. Hard to get to actionable solutions. Needs to be iterative - which is resource intensive.
- Users who want data may not know who the EDS are and how to access the relevant things. How do we find them?

Benefit/s:

- Services will be better suited to the people using them
- Staff will have examples/guidance they can learn from

Tips and advice from workshop attendees

- Don't treat / exploit users just as a resource for making things better. Get to know them and collaborate.
- Integrate user testing at every stage, even with rough wireframes. This validates design choices early on.
- Make the intangible tangible. This could be through personas, workflows, wireframes, fully interactive prototypes and more. Without a focal point for discussion it is too easy for different people to have very different ideas about the end goal.
- A tip (not necessarily top): setting out with a clear objective to be achieved or worked on with the user engagement undertaking is key to clarity for users being engaged with. Doing user engagement without a clear objective can do more harm than good.
- No top tip of my own, but I lean heavily on the [Turing Way guide for Communication/Community](#).

- Show that the feedback is being taken on board and actioned where appropriate and explain how the feedback is being used.
- Using drawtoast.com to gather and prioritise stakeholder requirements
- Implement requested changes quickly so that users feel their feedback is valued, which we've found helps in getting more feedback in the future
- Ensure the user engagement recognises the users interests and is focussed on creating value for the user.
- Regular, accessible and timely communication between users and those developing new tools and services so they are part of the process. I have seen this work well in other organisations e.g. DataCite but haven't managed it yet at our organisation

Workshop outputs

The key outputs from the workshop are:

- A list of prioritised development activities for user focussed services
- A list of case studies for WP5 of BOOST-EDS

List of prioritised development activities for user focussed services

Attendees were asked, ahead of the workshop, to identify priority areas for their teams and note them in a spreadsheet. There were issues with granularity of the identified activities, so it was not possible to prioritise this. However, the list was helpful for getting people talking during the workshop and identifying possible case studies.

List of case studies for WP5 of BOOST-EDS

During the workshop discussions, different categories for the case studies were identified:

- Data ingestion
- Data access
- User management
- Service management
 - including deprecating existing services - working out feasibility/scoping out
- User requirements/journeys
 - Drawing connections between our data/services/expertise. How to signpost people to the right place. Targeting services for specific user requirements.
 - New users

Next steps will be to confirm which case studies to develop through the remainder of the project. It is likely that we will choose a maximum of five case studies - one from each of the categories listed above.

The following list will need to be discussed and agreed with the WP5 working group. Initial ideas are as follows:

Case study category	Suggested case study	Is this work already planned or happening?	Who to co-create this with?	Contact within EDS	Additional notes
Data ingestion	Getting the data in example - BODC submission app.	Yes	Users of the data/tools/s ervices Data centre staff	Monica Hanley (BODC)	
Data access	EREDAP - Considering using EREDAP as API as entry point to access all the data- will be able to build a user interface. User interface tool on the top would be the thing that is for co-creation.	No?	Users of the data/tools/s ervices Data centre staff	BODC? Raised in Wendy's focus group - ask Wendy	
Data access	Downloads - could we simplify by just having a simple service across the EDS. This would make the EDS service easier to understand	No	Users of the data/tools/s ervices		
User management	A user registry "meta-service" that provides visibility of those who will be interacting with the EDS.	No	Users of the data/tools/s ervices Data centre staff		This will support easier engagement for the purposes of identifying potential collaborators.
User management	CEDA Archive accounts portal development	Yes	Users of the data/tools/s ervices Data centre staff	Sam Pepler / Andrew Harwood (CEDA)	
Service management	Create a catalogue of tools and services. Discovery and search for tools and services. This would be a good way to see similar	No	Users of the data/tools/s ervices Data centre		

	functionality of services.		staff		
User journeys	Website review - Create user requirements for accessing data (based on different user personas/typologies)	Yes	Users of the data Data centre staff	Carl Watson (BGS)	Access data example - User journeys - BGS example. In the next year. User typologies (personas). Selected BGS personas created for another project - https://britishgeologicalsurvey.github.io/ui-ux/personas/
?	DRI Futures / Datalabs Enhancements project	Yes	?	David Green / Kelly Widdicks (CEH)	

Next steps and actions:

- Ask attendees to review workshop summary report to ensure completeness and accuracy
- Set up working group with key interested experts - to shape the case studies/recommendations/guidelines
- Confirm use cases (and their leads). Decide how to interact with them over the next ~10 months. Draft timeline for when 'reports' are needed from each - which will feed into the guidelines produced at the end of the project.
- Identify who/how to include expert users in each case study. Create some text that could be used by the case study leads to encourage the expert users to engage with the co-creation process.

Anticipated outputs from WP5

Short report (April 2024 - this report!)

- about the outcomes from the workshop and proposed next steps

Case studies (May 2024 onwards)

- Confirm chosen case studies (likely to be other WPs from BOOST-EDS, could be wider)
- Include expert users to co-create the chosen activities

Guidelines for co-creating user-focussed services (April 2025)

- based on the example case studies, with recommendations for what worked well/didn't